

MODERN METHODS AND TOOLS FOR COMBATING THREATS TO YOUTH SPIRITUALITY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the threats directed against the spirituality of youth, their root causes, and their impact on society. It highlights how the intensified flow of information in the age of globalization, along with harmful ideas disseminated through the Internet and social networks, can negatively affect the spiritual worldview of young people. Furthermore, the article examines modern methods and tools for protecting youth from such threats, fostering a strong spiritual immunity, and nurturing them based on national values. The roles of the education system, family, mass media, and social institutions in this endeavor are specifically emphasized.

Keywords: youth, spirituality, spiritual threats, globalization, information security, spiritual immunity, national values, upbringing, internet and social networks, ideological threats.

The upbringing of youth, as one of the most important spheres determining the development of society, is constantly at the center of attention in our country. Because only young people who have achieved spiritual perfection and are committed to high moral standards will be able to further develop society in the future. However, in today's globalization process, many threats aimed at the spirituality of youth are observed. Among them are information attacks, various ideological influences, attempts to spread the ideas of extremism and terrorism, poisoning the mind by making alien beliefs attractive, and abusing the attention of young people through the Internet. The issue of preventing such threats and combating them with the help of modern methods and means is considered today as one of the most priority tasks from a scientific, practical, and educational point of view. As young people participate equally in various information spheres, the formation of critical thinking skills, raising the culture of information security, and educating them in close connection with our national values are fundamental priorities that must be emphasized in our continuously developing society. Therefore, the formation of immunity against various spiritual threats among young people has become relevant for scientific circles, educational institutions, and the institution of the family as a requirement of our time.

The development of modern technologies has brought the scale of information exchange to a completely new level. For instance, while obtaining information from the global network was a complex process several decades ago, now with the rapid development of the internet, almost every household and every age has the opportunity to use modern electronic devices. These conveniences are also an important factor in the formation of certain needs in the minds of young people. However, this process can also bring many risks. Because the flow of information is so large that it contains various ideologically harmful materials, currents that constantly try to deceive young people and lead them towards alien ideas. Certain groups pursuing material or political interests, taking advantage of these conditions, strive to promote

ideas that mislead the younger generation, contradict our national values, and harm the development of our society. Therefore, to preserve the spirituality of young people, it is necessary, first of all, to protect them from threats emanating from the internet space. In this regard, undoubtedly, the improvement of information culture, the improvement of online educational programs, the observance of ethical norms in the virtual world, the use of important educational mechanisms in it are recognized as the most effective manifestation of modern methods of struggle.

When identifying threats directed against the spirituality of youth on the global scale of Internet propaganda, a scientific study of the problem of strengthening spiritual stability is required. Because in today's information interpretation, various manifestations such as humorous appearances, malicious false news, conspiracies, extremist calls, and ideological provocations try to capture the consciousness of young people. For example, some categories aim to attract public attention with content that appears as mere jokes but actually damages the dignity of our religion or national traditions and raises doubts in young people's hearts. Behind such "humorous" aspects lie dangerous ideas. For this purpose, it is important to develop young people's skills in critically reviewing information, identifying sources of information, and verifying the authenticity of information. This is recognized as one of the most effective methods against modern information attacks. Because a young person with the ability to think critically has the opportunity to understand the essence of any idea, see its negative consequences, and determine its true purpose before accepting it. In this direction, the organization of media literacy lessons, scientific and practical seminars, and interactive classes on online safety measures in educational institutions is of particular importance as a means of modern struggle.

The institution of the family also plays an important role in the upbringing of young people. Because in the family, the first moral criteria of the child, his attitude to values, interest in reading, and the ability to think independently begin to form. If information security, spiritual stability, national traditions, and moral rules are not properly instilled in the family during the upbringing process, it will be easy to direct the minds of young people as desired. Therefore, it is advisable to use modern pedagogical methods in family upbringing, conduct open conversations with children, and encourage them to critically review any information. Technological progress requires rapid information exchange between family members as well. Therefore, parents themselves should pay attention to the possibility of rational use of the Internet, sorting foreign information, and obtaining in-depth knowledge together with children on various online educational platforms. Only then will a strong immunity be formed in the minds of young people, not in the form of continuous explanations, but through the ability to voluntarily sort each piece of information, it will be possible to protect against conspiracies directed against our spirituality.

In today's world politics, the spread of the ideas of extremism and terrorism is recognized as one of the most dangerous threats directed against youth. This vice is interpreted in scientific literature as an abstract idea that fights against one country or one people. However, in practice, it is clearly evident that it has a certain ideological or political purpose. Such a worldview, which is gradually formed in the minds of young people, leads to aggression, justification of illegal actions, and rejection of the need to obey the law. Therefore, in order to eradicate terrorism and extremism in the upbringing of young people, constant awareness-raising work should be

organized in educational institutions and public organizations. In this regard, strengthening in the minds of young people such concepts as patriotism, tolerance, and solidarity between peoples is interpreted as the main task. In the context of modern information technologies, special programs, interactive games, and various scientific and educational online projects can be used for this purpose. Because young people keep up with the times, traditional forms of propaganda may seem boring to them, but materials presented using modern means that are intense, somewhat intriguing, but based on accurate scientific sources, attract more attention. Thus, if historical activity, national traditions, spiritual heritage are conveyed to young people in harmony with modern cultural achievements, then a sense of belonging to various alien ideas will increase in them.

In order to enrich its essence with a scientific approach, various initiatives are also being harmonized in the educational process. For example, such methods as forming high spirituality in the younger generation through literary works, awakening a sense of national pride by studying the lives of historical figures, and promoting the heritage of our poets and writers, which are read with love in our society, in a new form can yield solid results in the upbringing of young people. At the same time, the goal of training qualified specialists who can respond with scientific evidence to any foreign ideas through in-depth study of foreign languages will also be accelerated. Because only when spirituality, culture, and scientific knowledge unite will it be possible to adequately counter the emerging ideological threats in our society. In this process, many methods can be used, such as various scientific centers, educational libraries, interactive projects in the library, ideological trainings, and the promotion of reading among young people. The main goal is that every young person should be able to understand the state of information, freely express their opinion, make correct decisions based on critical thinking, and develop as a person who has matured in the information space.

One of the aspects requiring special attention is the development of effective means of promotion. For example, it is necessary to ensure open communication with young people through television programs, radio broadcasts, virtual marathons, that is, live broadcasts in information networks. Since many young people are active in media networks, it will be effective to organize regular promotional activities, scientific conversations, and Q&As in those areas. Through this, they can not just listen to issues that cause various doubts or debates, but directly discuss them with experts and draw necessary conclusions for themselves. At the same time, through competitions held in virtual space, initiatives such as the best article or the best video, it is possible to create an active position in the minds of young people to combat threats. In this process, along with the promotion of the heritage of our ancestors, created on the basis of national values, the world scientific heritage, achievements of modern science, and results achieved in the field of information technologies are also manifested as a wide range of opportunities required in the upbringing of the younger generation.

Currently, cooperation with influencers, bloggers, and influential experts to strengthen ideological immunity through the mass media, in particular, social networks, is of particular importance. Because young people mostly follow the activities of bloggers, they perceive them primarily as friends, brothers, or ideals close to them. Therefore, it is advisable to systematically cover alternative information sources through leading bloggers who are in the public eye, to cite and emphasize arguments from legal, political, and educational aspects regarding various ideological threats. However, haste or unscientific approaches in this process can, on the

contrary, arouse suspicion in young people. Therefore, the scientific sources that bloggers rely on should be strong, the information should be explained with well-founded arguments, presented in harmony with our national heritage and international recommendations. Although young people perceive information immediately, substantiated materials have the strongest impact on conveying its essence. In this way, the ability to avoid negative propaganda from the surrounding environment, to scientifically evaluate them using modern opportunities, and to see to what extent the goals of interested parties are planned in advance is formed.

In conclusion, modern methods and means of protecting the spirituality of youth must be constantly improved. Because the threats also manifested themselves in new forms and approaches. Ideological attacks that were once spread on paper or made through radio and television explanations are now entering through internet networks, mobile applications, and even special programs. The consciousness of young people can maintain stability in such a relationship with the ability to critically see reality and draw the right conclusions. Therefore, the main task is to improve the quality of education, strengthen spiritual education in the family, identify talented youth in cooperation with public organizations, and provide them with targeted support. Only when all of this is implemented as a unified system will young people, the owners of our future, be guaranteedly protected from the influence of various alien ideas. In the modern world, professional activity in the information space as a means of struggle, the development of necessary methods based on scientific and practical experiments, and the reformation of educational processes by harmonizing national and world experience are of paramount importance. Modern means, along with technological protection conditions, must provide for the training of moral immunity. Only then will a systematic, logical approach be formed in preventing threats to the spirituality of youth.

In our society, along with the attention paid to young people, skills such as independent thinking, the ability to choose a fair path, and the scientific assessment of the dangers that information conceals are being strengthened. In this process, it is considered an urgent task to act together from the education system to the family environment and all public organizations, to direct all the tools involved against the negative influences that are being intensively carried out in the information space in one direction. For this purpose, special methods have been developed, disciplined plans in media sources, mechanisms for selecting confidential information, and approaches such as presenting complex scientific thought in a simple but substantiated form, understandable to young people. With the help of these approaches, it is envisaged, on the one hand, to educate young people as spiritually mature individuals, and on the other hand, to increase their ability to consciously fight against various destructive ideas. New pedagogical technologies, consultations, and information management methods, which provide for various adaptation mechanisms, are also among them.

In educational institutions, it is possible to increase the spiritual strength of youth education not only within the framework of a certain subject or direction, but also through an interdisciplinary approach. Because if a certain concept is given within the framework of one science, this concept becomes clearer when combined with the data of other sciences. For example, in a history lesson, the development of our national statehood, the values of our ancestors, and their courage are told, while in a literature lesson, poems or educational works created during that period are perceived in the students' minds together. This allows not only to know historical information, but also to deeply understand the spirit and values of that time.

In this way, young people develop a love for our national heritage, and it becomes easier to understand what the threats against it are actually aimed at. Modern media can bring historical scientific information to life through specific audio, video, and interactive forms, creating equal opportunities for young people with disabilities. Only with such a unified approach will young people feel united in the fight against threats, their historical memory and sense of responsibility for the future will increase.

It should be noted that threats directed against the spirituality of youth can manifest themselves in many ways. Identifying one loser or culprit doesn't solve the problem. Because among the population, there is a possibility that various opinions, concepts, and discussions can lead to neglect in the upbringing of children or the culture of communication, leading the minds of young people astray. Today, the most important priority task is to raise young people in a system of upbringing with such an open worldview, but at the same time provided with national moral views. After all, no matter how widespread the information is, no matter how attractive it is, young people with critical thinking, knowledge, and moral stability can find their way in this trend without getting lost. A generation that has developed a sense of independent thinking, clearly knows the boundaries of its values, can study any scientific source and draw correct conclusions, will firmly protect society from political or ideological threats. Therefore, a systematic approach is necessary in the fight against any threat directed against the spirituality of youth. In it, state policy, the education system, the family environment, public organizations, cooperation in the media sphere, and most importantly, the conscious immunity that is formed in each young person, must be constantly developed. Thus, in today's information age, the continuous improvement of modern methods and tools to prevent threats directed against the spirituality of youth is an important task at all levels. The main goal is to ensure information security in our society, replace various alien ideas with science and enlightenment, harmonize our national heritage with the world scientific heritage, and form a conscious worldview among young people. Each of us is responsible for this, because the spiritual development of future generations is not just the task of one institution or agency, but a collective matter connected with a sense of responsibility for the development of our entire society. Through such a comprehensive and effective approach, scientifically based methods, innovative technologies, and mechanisms for increasing the potential of independent critical thinking, it is possible to achieve success in preserving and strengthening the spirituality of youth. Undoubtedly, in the future, our efforts in this direction will be consolidated, and advanced methods that compete with world experience, but do not lose national identity, will be improved. Thus, the spiritual foundations forming in the minds of young people protect them from various threats and encourage them to actively work for the prosperity of our society.

In the process of reforms being implemented in the New Uzbekistan, large-scale work is being carried out in order to comprehensively modernize the life of society, improve the legal, political, and spiritual environment based on democratic principles. Within the framework of these reforms, the issue of educating young people, protecting them from various threats directed against spirituality, and protecting our children from sources attempting to poison their minds in the modern information space is of paramount importance. Indeed, today, in the process of globalization, along with the growth of information networks, there is a comprehensive intensification of ideological, information-psychological threats, such as extremism and terrorism, forms of ideological struggle in the information space, which can

disrupt the psyche of young people. Therefore, among the reforms we are witnessing in New Uzbekistan, ways to protect the spirituality of youth and protect them from various threats are being further improved.

The concept of spirituality, on the one hand, encompasses national values, historical roots, national pride, spiritual heritage, and religious-humanistic principles, and on the other hand, in harmony with global integration processes, plays an important role in the process of forming modern thinking in the thinking of the younger generation. However, in today's digital world, when various ideological currents spreading through the Internet and information that can create worldview conflicts in the minds of young people are increasing, one of the most important issues is to filter them, identify threats that may harm spirituality, and talk about means of combating them.

The reforms being implemented in the New Uzbekistan based on the principle of "For Human Dignity" are aimed, first of all, at ensuring the rights and freedoms of every citizen. In this process, raising the spirituality of youth, educating them as a generation with scientific potential, intellectually developed, imbued with national values and universal ideas, is recognized as one of the main priorities. In this regard, within the framework of the Five Important Initiatives put forward by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a number of important projects are being implemented, such as the meaningful organization of young people's leisure time, familiarizing them with our cultural heritage, widely involving them in sports, fostering friendship with information technologies, and promoting reading. Through such measures, the mechanism for strengthening the spiritual world of our youth and protecting them from vile vices is also being strengthened.

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